

Polarographic behaviour of 3-(1-phenyl)-1-(2'-hydroxynaphthyl)-2-propen-1-one and thermodynamic parameters of complexes of bivalent transition metal ions

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Manuscript received 12 March 2003, revised 10 November 2003, accepted 18 February 2004

The electrochemical reduction behaviour of 3-(1-phenyl)-1-(2'-hydroxynaphthyl)-2-propen-1-one (PHPO) has been studied in aq. DMF media of pH 2.0 to 12.0 by d.c. polarography. Diffusion coefficient (D) of the electrode process has been calculated. The stability constants of UO_2^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Mn^{2+} complexes of PHPO have been determined in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water, acetone-water and 2-ethoxyethanol-water mixture using the Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique as developed by Irving and Rossotti. The stability constants are in fair agreement with Irving-Williams order. The results obtained are compared with electrochemical reduction behaviour of PHPO and also with the data available in the literature. Abnormal behaviour of the chelates was observed in acetone-water medium. The thermodynamic parameters such as free energy, enthalpy and entropy changes involved in complexation have been calculated.

In continuation of our earlier work¹⁻⁴ on reduction behaviour of ligands and stability constants and the thermodynamic parameters of metal chelates, here, I calculated and compared the electrochemical reduction behaviour of PHPO with stability constants and the thermodynamic parameters of the complexes of UO_2^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Mn^{2+} at different temperature employing polarographic technique and Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique⁵⁻⁷, as modified by Irving and Rossotti³.

Results and discussion

The PHPO was reduced in presence of DMF over the whole pH range 2.0 to 12.0. The ligand exhibits two reduction waves in acidic and neutral media (pH 2 to 6) and an additional wave in strongly alkaline media (pH 8). At first stage, two electron reduction waves correspond to the reduction of the ethylenic linkage to dihydro derivative and the third wave is attributed to the reduction of the carbonyl group to the corresponding secondary alcohol. The slope of E vs. $\log (i/i_d - i)$ graph exceeds appreciably $59/n$ mV and the numerical value of $E_{1/4} - E_{3/4}$ exceeds $56.4/n$ mV. The variation in the proportion of the organic solvent (DMF) from 50 to 70% causes a decrease in i_d values, which may be partly due to an increase in the viscosity of the medium and absorption of solvent molecules on the electrode surface.

In PHPO, the phenyl group was directly linked to the ethylenic double bond ($-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{ph}$). If the phenyl group contains electron withdrawing group (or) releasing group, it will influence the $E_{1/2}$ values of the $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ reduc-

tion, but it will not affect the reduction potential of keto group in PHPO, which was observed in our earlier work²⁻⁴. However in PHPO, there was no electron withdrawing (or) releasing group. In our earlier work¹, phenyl group containing one $-\text{Cl}$ in position 4 is adjacent to the $>\text{C}=\text{C}<$, that will have more half wave potential than phenyl group containing two $-\text{OCH}_3$ groups in position 3, 4 because electron density was decreased at the reactive center ($>\text{C}=\text{C}<$). But in the case of PHPO, $E_{1/2}$ value was less than that of phenyl group containing $-\text{Cl}$ but more than that of phenyl group containing two $-\text{OCH}_3$ group in position 3 and 4. It is evident that the reduction process was difficult in PHPO to compare to that of phenyl group containing $-\text{Cl}$, but reduction process was easy in PHPO to compare to that of phenyl group containing two $-\text{OCH}_3$ groups in position 3 and 4.

From the titration curves, the stability constant of UO_2^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Mn^{2+} with 3-(1-phenyl)-1-(2'-hydroxynaphthyl)-2-propen-1-one (PHPO) were calculated employing the method reported earlier^{2,7,8,10}.

The formation of metal chelates took place by replacement of hydrogen of the 2-hydroxynaphthyl group and coordination occurs through the oxygen of the ketonic group. The acid dissociation constant of the ligand was found to decrease in different media in the order dioxane > acetone > 2-ethoxyethanol. A plot of pk_L against $1/D$ was linear. However, in acetone-water solvent the dissociation constant of the ligand is less than the expected

value and it may be attributed to the non-ideal behaviour of acetone-water solvent. The order of stability of the metal chelates in all the three solvents was observed as $\text{UO}_2^{2+} > \text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Mn}^{2+}$. This order of stability follows the Irving-Williams¹¹ natural order except cobalt(II) leading to the conclusion that the ligand used in the present investigation is weak field one. The greater stability of cobalt(II) chelate when compared to nickel(II) chelate may be attributed to the additional stabilization due to John-Teller distortion present in the former case. The order cobalt(II) > nickel(II) has been reported for some other ligands^{2,3,12-14}. The values of $\log \beta$ for zinc(II) chelates are greater than those of nickel(II). The order zinc(II) > nickel(II) has been observed earlier also^{1,2,11,15} where the relative low value for nickel(II) has been attributed to the presence of a square-planar structure. Further the hydrolysis constant of zinc(II) chelate is greater than that of nickel(II) which indicates a greater affinity of zinc(II) for -OH ions. This factor seems to be accurate for the order zinc(II) > nickel(II). The order of stability of complexes with respect to the solvent in dioxane > acetone > 2-ethoxyethanol. The dielectric constants for the pure as well as mixed solvent are in the order acetone > 2-ethoxyethanol > dioxane. This also shows the abnormal behaviour of acetone-water mixture, similar abnormality was reported in the literature^{1,2,11,15,16}.

According to stability constants, the difference between $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ values are small and the ratio of $\log k_1/\log k_2$ is positive in all cases indicating that there is little (or) no steric hindrance to the addition of the second ligand molecule. It is compared with $E_{1/2}$ value of PHPO and stability constants of metal chelates with PHPO. The ligand which has more $E_{1/2}$ value has less $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ values for metal chelates. This was also observed in our earlier report¹⁻⁴. Hence, we can conclude that the ligand which has more reduction potential ($E_{1/2}$) value, shows less stability constant values for bivalent transition metal complexes.

The thermodynamic parameters free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) change have been calculated¹⁷ from the stability constants of the metal complexes determined at three different temperature (30, 35 and 40°) in 75% dioxane. The ΔG values are all negative and suggest that complexation is a spontaneous process. The negative ΔH values for complex formation indicate the release of energy during the interaction of metal ions with ligand. The ΔH values of the complex formation of PHPO with metal complexes follows the order $\text{UO}_2^{2+} > \text{Cu}^{2+} >$

$\text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Mn}^{2+}$ in agreement with the natural order of the stability constants. The values of ΔS are positive for all the systems indicating that entropy is favourable for the complex formation.

Experimental

The ligand 3-(1-phenyl)-1-(2'-hydroxynaphthyl)-2-propen-1-one (PHPO) was prepared by the condensation of 2-hydroxy-1-acetonaphthone with benzaldehyde⁵. The purity of the sample was checked by elemental analyses. The solution of the ligand was prepared using dioxane, acetone and 2-ethoxyethanol as solvent. The metal nitrate solutions were prepared in CO_2 free doubly distilled water and were standardized by standard methods⁹. Dioxane, acetone and 2-ethoxyethanol were purified before use.

Polarographic measurements for PHPO were carried out with an Elico CL 25 polarographic analyzer at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. An Elico (< 1-120) digital pH meter was used for pH measurements.

Procedure :

Polarographic measurements for PHPO were carried out at the rate of 2.88 mg s^{-1} in the presence of DMF, saturated calomel reference and platinum counter electrodes were used. Universal buffer of pH 2.0 to 12.0 were prepared by using 0.2 M boric acid, 0.05 M citric acid and 0.1 M trisodium orthophosphate.

The stability constants of UO_2^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Mn^{2+} complexes with 3-(1-phenyl)-1-(2'-hydroxynaphthyl)-2-propen-1-one (PHPO) were determined by using pH titration of the following carbonate free solution of 50 ml at the desired temperatures against standard sodium hydroxide. (a) 5 ml of 0.1 M KNO_3 + 37.5 ml organic solvent + 5 ml 0.01 M HNO_3 + 2.5 ml water. (b) 5 ml of 0.1 M KNO_3 + 1 ml of 0.1 M ligand in pure organic solvent + 36.5 ml organic solvent + 5 ml 0.01 M HNO_3 + 2.5 ml water. (c) 5 ml of 0.1 M KNO_3 + 1 ml of 0.1 M ligand solution + 36.5 ml organic solvent + 5 ml 0.01 M HNO_3 + 0.5 ml of (1.01 M) metal solution + 2 ml water.

The pH values (B) were corrected in all the aqua-organic mixture by the method of Van Uiter and Hass⁵ ($-\log [\text{H}^+] B + \log U_H$) and others⁶. Under the present conditions the following $\log U_H$ values were obtained in different media under consideration : 0.36 (75% aq. dioxane), 0.29 (75% aq. acetone) and 0.24 (75% aq. 2-ethoxyethanol).

Acknowledgement

The author thanks Dr. R. Seshadri Naidu, Director, Academic Staff College, S V University, Tirupathi, Dr N. S Reddi, Principal, JNV, Peddapuram and K Ramu Reddy, PGT English, JNV, Peddapuram for their valuable suggestions

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